

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

BigDataForAll

Promoting Statistics and Big Data through Gamification and Digital Education

#BIGDATAFORALL

2021-2023

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Intellectual Products

Outcomes of the project

Intellectual Products

MOOC on Gamification Processes

A MOOC on how to design, implement and evaluate gamification processes for daily teaching in higher education (especially Statistics and Big Data).

Educational Game on Statistics and Big Data

An educational game of virtual learning (through a web platform) aimed at training university students in Statistics and Big Data. This process of gamification will be a personalized training itinerary according to the competencies required by companies and social organizations in both matters

#BIGDATAFORALL

MOOC

Gamification in Higher Education

Instructional Design
Theory/Practice
Evaluation
Supporting materials

**1. WHAT IS
GAMIFICATION**

**2. HOW TO DESIGN A
GAMIFICATION
PROCESS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION**

**3. HOW TO CARRY OUT
A GAMIFICATION
PROCESS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION**

**4. HOW TO ASSESS A
GAMIFICATION
PROCESS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION**

**5. CREATION OF A
GAMIFICATION
PROCESS ON
STATISTICS AND
BIG DATA**

**6. TIPS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS**

#BIGDATAFORALL

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Intellectual Products

MOOC on
Gamification
Processes

Educational Game on
Statistics and Big
Data

**What do you know about statistics
and professional profiles?**

#BIGDATAFORALL

Educational game

Statistics and Big Data

What is...

Statistics?

Statistics is the science of collecting, analyzing and understanding data, and accounting for the relevant uncertainties.

As such, it permeates the physical, natural and social sciences; public health; medicine; business; and policy.

Big Data?

Big Data is the collection and analysis of data sets that are complex in terms of the volume and variety, and in some cases the velocity at which they are collected. Big data problems usually require multidisciplinary teams by their very nature.

At the very least, they typically require subject area (domain) experts, computational experts, machine learning experts AND statisticians.

#BIGDATAFORALL

Educational game

Statistics and Big Data

The **Data Entrepreneur**
(generate business strategies through data analysis)

The **Statistician**
(narrate and interpret the data)

The **Data Engineer**
(scale the data)

The **Data Architect** (create secure databases)

The **Data Scientist**
(extract information from databases)

The **Data Analyst** (process data)

Educational game

Statistics and Big Data

Project manager

Responsible of extracting data, pre-processing them (data cleaning, normalisation, identification of missing values or noise), transforming and synthesising the information contained in them (for example, descriptive analysis, like frequencies and descriptives measurements)

Engineer

Its main role is to collect the needs transmitted by the business and present the results obtained in previous phases to generate business strategies.

Architect

The statistician is in charge of interpreting, narrating and communicating the results obtained in previous phases in order to extract valuable information translated into the company/business context.

Statistician

Entrepreneur

The technical role is in charge of setting up the technological infrastructure so that the large volume of unstructured data collected becomes accessible raw material for analysts and data scientists.

This is in charge of the aspects associated with the origin of the data. That is to say, the handling and management of the location of the data. He/she is in charge of the proper functioning of the infrastructure where the volume of data is located and from where it will be extracted.

Scientist

Responsible for setting up the data science project, coordinating the whole group to work collaboratively and closing the circle of work

Professional dedicated to completing the initial analyses performed by the data analyst at a more complex level (multiple variables), (for example, prediction, regression models, cluster analysis...)

Analyst

Educational game

Statistics and Big Data

Project manager

Architect

Engineer

Analyst

Scientist

Statistician

Entrepreneur

This is in charge of the aspects associated with the origin of the data. That is to say, the handling and management of the location of the data. He/she is in charge of the proper functioning of the infrastructure where the volume of data is located and from where it will be extracted.

Responsible for setting up the data science project, coordinating the whole group to work collaboratively and closing the circle of work

Responsible of extracting data, pre-processing them (data cleaning, normalisation, identification of missing values or noise), transforming and synthesising the information contained in them (for example, descriptive analysis, like frequencies and descriptives measurements)

The technical role is in charge of setting up the technological infrastructure so that the large volume of unstructured data collected becomes accessible raw material for analysts and data scientists.

The statistician is in charge of interpreting, narrating and communicating the results obtained in previous phases in order to extract valuable information translated into the company/business context.

Professional dedicated to completing the initial analyses performed by the data analyst at a more complex level (multiple variables), (for example, prediction, regression models, cluster analysis...)

Its main role is to collect the needs transmitted by the business and present the results obtained in previous phases to generate business strategies.

#BIGDATAFORALL

Educational game

OFFLINE VERSION

**What better way to see it than
playing!**

#BIGDATAFORALL

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Intellectual Products

**What have you learnt about
statistics professional profiles?**

Intellectual Products

Playing this game you not only learn about statistics and Big Data, you work your personal soft skills, like:

Critical thinking
Communication
Work in groups
English

Educational game

ONLINE VERSION

#BIGDATAFORALL

Thanks for your attention!

PARTNERS

CO-FUNDED

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Promoting Statistics and Big Data through Gamification and Digital Education © 2022 • COPYRIGHT

The project 2020-1-ES01-KA226-HE-095688 has been funded with support from the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Commission. This publication website reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.